

Thermodynamics of V(V)-7-Chloro-8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-Sulphonate

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Vanadium (V) forms in aqueous medium, a 1 : 2 complex with 7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid with λ_{\max} at 360 nm, stable in the pH range 5.6-7.6. The stability constant and free energy of formation of the complex are found to be $\log K = 10.49 \pm 0.20$ and $\Delta F = -14.55 \pm 0.28$ kcal/mole at 30°. The enthalpy change and entropy change calculated by temperature coefficient method and Gibb's-Helmholtz equation are found to be -21.97 kcal/mole and -25.23 e.u. respectively.

For the analysis of metal ions, 8-hydroxyquinoline is a well known reagent. By condensation and substitution reactions, certain groups can be introduced into the molecule of this compound so as to modify its complex-forming properties. Many metal ions do not form a precipitate but change colour with 7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid. Tiao-Hsu Chang and co-workers¹ have studied the stability constants of chelates of 7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid with Ni, Co, Zn, Pb and Cd potentiometrically, but no significant work on its vanadium chelate is on record. The present study deals with the investigation of V(V)-7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid chelate spectrophotometrically regarding its composition, stability and thermodynamic parameters like ΔF , ΔH and ΔS , associated with the formation of the complex in aqueous medium.

Preparation of the reagent, metal solutions and the experimental details are similar to those described in our earlier publication².

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The effective pH range for the stable existence of the complex was found to be between 5.6-7.6. However, pH 6.6 ± 0.1 was selected for subsequent studies, as the complex showed maximum extinction at this pH. Ammonium acetate buffer was used to maintain the constant pH.

The nature of the complex was studied by the method of Vosburgh and Cooper³ and it was found that only one complex is formed under the conditions of study, with λ_{\max} at 360 nm.

The empirical formula of the complex in solution was established by three independent methods, the Continuous Variation method⁴, Mole-ratio method⁵ and Slope-ratio method⁶.

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The results indicate that one mole of vanadium reacts with two moles of the reagent to form a stable complex in solution.

The stability constant of the complex has been calculated by the method of Banerji and Dey⁷, mole-ratio method and the method using molecular extinction-coefficient data. The values obtained by these different methods are in close agreement and the mean value of $\log K = 10.49 \pm 0.20$ and the free energy of formation comes out to be $\Delta F = -14.55 \pm 0.28$ kcals./mole at 30°.

In view of the difficulty in obtaining thermodynamic stability constant (and hence ΔF), we have determined the stability constant and free energy of formation of the complex at a fixed ionic strength of 0.1 M, pH 6.6 ± 0.1 and at various temperatures. The results obtained, have been presented in Table I.

TABLE I

Log K, ΔF , and ΔS at various temperatures

Temp. °C	Log K	ΔF Kcals.	ΔS e.u.
30	10.35	-14.34	-25.19
35	10.05	-14.17	-25.32
40	9.82	-14.06	-25.27
45	9.58	-13.95	-25.23
50	9.34	-13.80	-25.29
55	9.13	-13.71	-25.19
60	8.93	-13.60	-25.14
		Average	-25.23

From the slope of the curve obtained by plotting $\log K$ against $1/T$ (Fig. 1), the enthalpy change (ΔH) of the reaction calculated by temperature-coefficient method was found to be -21.97 kcals./mole. Assuming this to be constant over the range of the temperatures employed, entropy change (ΔS) of the reaction has also been calculated, using Gibb's-Helmholtz equation and has been found to be -25.23 e.u.

FIG. 1

Fig. 1. Variation of $\log K$ with $1/T$.

A comparison of the stability constant and free energy of formation of Vanadium (V)-7-Chloro-8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid chelate ($\log K = 10.49 \pm 0.20$; $\Delta F = -14.55 \pm 0.28$) with the corresponding Vanadium-(V)-7-Bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid chelate² ($\log K = 10.61 \pm 0.30$; $\Delta F = -14.71 \pm 0.41$) reveals that the bromo derivative of 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid forms more stable complexes than the corresponding chloro derivative. The order is in accordance with the results obtained by Tiao-Hsu Chang and co-workers¹. It may be due to the fact that the chloro derivative is more acidic than the bromo derivative.

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